

WRENCH

Whispers of Time

Heritage as Narratives of Climate Change

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Anti-harassment and discrimination policy for WRENCH

Vision and guidelines

*Prepared for the kick-off meeting of
WRENCH, UAB, iHC
Barcelona, 18,19 October 2024*

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A Belmont Forum Project

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our vision

“A good research environment is not only defined by the efficiency of the research group. As part of the team that coordinates WRENCH, we believe that it is crucial to take the time to discuss how we are committed to ensuring that the project is carried out in a way that prevents any harassment, discrimination, or unethical behaviour. We are sure that there is a common feeling among us with regard to this matter. To this end, we have prepared this brief guide, which complements the internal rules of each partner participating in WRENCH and the rules applicable in each geographical area where WRENCH is being developed.”

Ethical principles:

we respect and encourage human relations based on diversities (of national origins, race, colour, ancestry, creed, religion, sex, gender identity or expression, age, physical or mental dis-ability, marital or domestic partnership status, affectional or sexual orientation, etc.). Similarly, we commit to respect and encourage more-than-human relations. We reject any exploitative behaviour, abuse of power, physical and verbal violence.

Working definitions.

Discrimination and exclusion: it is the adverse treatment of individuals on the basis of their characteristics, to the extent that they are not informed of the group's activities, are sidelined and do not have equal access to the group's resources and opportunities.

Harassment: it is the set of unwanted, severe or pervasive verbal, physical or sexual behaviours that have the effect of interfering with an individual's working or living conditions by creating an intimidating, hostile, offensive or violating environment.

Unethical behaviour: Discrimination, exclusion, harassment of any kind and any other behaviour that violates ethical principles.

Ethic in research and data management is also regulated under the Regulation (EU) 2016/679 General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)

guidelines and checklist

WRENCH aims to work in a horizontal, non-hierarchical asset. These principles apply both within the research group and in relation to activities undertaken with stakeholders and community members during interviews, focus groups and other fieldwork activities.

If you are a victim of or become aware of discrimination, harassment or any ethical violation within the WRENCH project, please report your complaint immediately to
-the P.I., Prof. Marco Armiero (armiero@icrea.cat)
or, if it is reasonable to inform another person, to
- the Chair of the WRENCH Advisory Board, Prof. Manuelina Maria Duarte Cândido (manuelin@uol.com.br).

Please keep asking yourself these questions when organising a meeting, focus group or other activity within the project.

- Did you get the needed permissions from your institution?
- Did you invite everyone on time?
- Did you respect their time zones and schedules?
- Are you giving back to the communities you are researching with?
- Have you considered gender balance?
- Representation of diversities?
- Are you self-reflective about your practices?

link and online resources

Regulation (EU) 2016/679

General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR)

<https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2016/679/oj>

European Data Protection Supervisor

Anti-harassment procedures

https://www.edps.europa.eu/data-protection/data-protection/reference-library/anti-harassment-procedures_en

European commission

Know your rights – Equality – Non-discrimination

https://commission.europa.eu/aid-development-cooperation-fundamental-rights/your-rights-eu/know-your-rights/equality/non-discrimination_en

Llei orgànica 3/2018, de 5 de desembre, de protecció de dades personals i garantidels drets digitals.

https://www.boe.es/boe_catalan/dias/2018/12/06/pdfs/BOE-A-2018-16673-C.pdf

UAB Policy against situations of gender and LGTBiphobic violence and other discriminations

<https://www.uab.cat/web/newsroom/news-detail/the-uab-approves-a-policy-document-to-address-situations-of-gender-violence-and-other-forms-of-discrimination-1345830290613.html?detid=1345915506251>

What is harassment and discrimination for you?

Interactive activity conducted during the kick-off meeting of WRENCH, UAB, iHC, Barcelona, 18,19 October 2024

"For me, harassment is habits or behaviors that may offend, or violate (physically or mentally) someone. I am used to associating it with sexual violence. Discrimination is a way to stay in our ignorance fighting everything or everybody different in culture, gender, habits"

"Harassment is for me any behavior that is violent in many ways – physically and verbally – and disrespectful. Discrimination is excluding the powerless".

"Harassment is when your behavior puts someone uncomfortable or makes someone scared. Discrimination is when you judge someone based on the group they belong to (ethnic/religion/gender)"

"Harassment is persuading and manipulating, is verbal pestering, not listening to other's views, feelings. Discrimination is preconceived ideas, automatic mining way to tell about myself, my protected characteristics."

"Harassment is the tendency of some workplaces (or higher-rank workers) to create work relationships which inhibit the full exploitation of capacity, enthusiasm, potential of colleagues, especially younger and more diverse ones. Discrimination is the act of making decisions about work division, tasks, distributions, or simpler ones about ordinary life, considering aspects that are not relevant to the case"

"Harassment is trying to make others feel uncomfortable or make them lose confidence. Discrimination is not giving equal opportunities to everyone"

"Harassment is behaviors that annoy the others. Discrimination is behaviors or discourses which will make other people feel excluded, negative, discouraged"

"Harassment and discrimination are the worst postures for a group of people, bullying behaviors"

"Harassment is when you force someone to do something he/she dislikes. Discrimination is when someone is excluded for his/her physical characteristics or different ideas"

"Harassment is a way to treat colleagues in a diminishing way, for example not considering difficulties, opinions, and needs when making decisions. Of course, harassment is any kind of violence, physical or psychological, linked to any type of discrimination (gender, race, physical abilities, and so on).

"Discrimination is the act of treating someone differently on the base of any reason. Harassment is the act of intruding on one's personal space without the will of that person either physically or mentally"

"Harassment is any form of abuse of power. In a male-dominated society, we often do not even recognize harassment. Harassment should not be defined by those in power but by those who are victims. Discrimination is conscious and unconscious bias based on unjust power relations".

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